

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF DAMAGE

ACCUMULATION IN NOTCHED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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Summary

The penetrant enhanced X-ray radiography and the nonlinear finite element method are used to analyze the process of damage accumulation and the damage zone growth in the notched graphite/epoxy laminates. The comparison of the numerical results and the experimental results is presented. It is found that the numerical method could well imitate the actual damage growth to certain degree under the condition of reasonable establishment of the constitutive relation of the materials after damage occurring.

Introduction

To the fracture of the notched composite laminates, it was discovered that there always was some damage to a degree in the notch tips before final failure and its effect to failure could be presented by a parameter (that is TWO PARAMETER fracture theories put forward in 1970s according to the linear elastic fracture mechanics, these theories required the use of crack length corrections to reflect the presence of damage zone). With the development of accurate nondestructive evaluation methods, it became apparent that these corrections were arbitrary and subject to question. As a result, some numerical methods were developed to model the actual damage accumulation process (1)(2)(3). Nevertheless, those work mainly dealt with the residual strength of materials, whether numerical model could be used to predict the real failure process of materials has not been clarified.

Herein, the penetrant enhanced X-ray radiography and the nonlinear finite element method have been used to analyze the damage accumulation in the graphite/epoxy composite laminates with cracks emanating from a central circular hole. The diagrams showing the growth and shapes of the ply damage zone at different loading levels are developed. The comparison between the numerical results and experimental results is presented and the results are discussed.

Experiments and Observation

Penetrant Enhanced X-ray Radiography

The penetrant enhanced X-ray radiography has been widely used to predict the damage accumulation process in fiber reinforced composite materials. These penetrants, such as tetrabromoethane(TBE), diiodobutane(DIB), and zinc iodide in an alcohol solution, are some liquid whose specific gravity and coefficient to absorb X-ray are larger than that of carbon and oxide. In the present study, the TBE is used. When the damage occurs in the composite laminates, the TBE can enter the void and delamination by capillary. In the X-ray records, the TBE can provide sufficient contrast between the damage and the graphite/epoxy so that the damage process could be observed.

The following procedure was used in making the X-ray radiographs presented herein:

1. The specimens were loaded to an assigned load and then removed from the tester. The TBE was applied continuously to the surfaces of the specimens in the damage region for 30 min to give it sufficient time to penetrate into all of the matrix cracks and delaminations. After it had fully saturated the damage region, the excess TBE was removed from the surfaces of specimens with clean cotton.
2. A 2005 - II type X-ray unit, operating at 45 kV and 5 mA, was used to expose the film. The film was exposed for 8 min.
3. Step 1 and step 2 were repeated for each desired load(50% - 100% failure load), so the damage at different loading levels can be observed.
4. The X-ray negatives were amplificatively printed on high contrast paper. This was done to bring out the fine detail in the damage region.

All the experiments were made on a Z/D - 90 Testing machine with a

crosshead speed of 1mm/min.

Cumulative Damage Development

The penetrant enhanced X-ray radiography procedure described in the previous section was used to document the damage accumulation process in the graphite/epoxy specimens used in Ref. 4. The specimens contain cracks emanating from a central hole or only a central hole (Fig. 1 shows the coordinate system). The reader is referred to Ref. 4 for a detail description of the specimens geometry.

Figure 1. Geometry and coordinate of the specimens

The penetrant enhanced X-ray radiographs of damage in Specimen CA1-1((0/90)_{4s} laminate) at different loading levels are shown in Fig. 2 through Fig. 4. The tensile strength of matrix in composite materials is very weak, the matrix cracks emanating from the crack tips primarily occurred in the 90-deg plies along fiber. Since the cracks were very short, the stress field away from crack tips was controlled by the hole so that the concentrated stress field was large and the matrix cracks also emanated from the edge of the hole. This damage zone which took the form of matrix cracks expanded very large as load increased.

As can be seen from the figures, the matrix cracks in the 90-deg plies did not place closely and there was a distance between each other. This is because there must be energy release and stress relaxation in the vicinity of a matrix crack when it appears due to the energy concentration. The new energy causing the new matrix crack to initiate could only concentrate at a distance. This phenomenon can also be observed in the failure process of unnotched laminates containing 90-deg ply.

In the 0-deg plies, the high stress in the region ahead of the notches is transmitted from one fiber group to another. Since the shear strength of matrix is relatively weak, the matrix cracks along fiber took place rapidly and expanded very long as load increased. because there is stress gradient in the front of crack tip, the matrix ahead of the cracks tip entered damage gradually and formed a region like an isosceles triangle. Owing to a large number of the matrix cracks taking place, the delaminations were finally introduced in this region (see Fig. 4).

After the damage appearing in the 0-deg and 90-deg plies, although there were few fiber fractures, the materials in each ply had lost the ability to

undertake shear stress due to the matrix failure. The low stress area in the region beside the hole in the load direction increased and the damage was not able to enter this region(Fig.4).

Figure 2 Radiographic image of ply damage at $0.507 S_c$ in Specimen CA1-1

Figure 3 Radiographic image of ply damage at $0.846 S_c$ in Specimen CA1-1

Summary of Experimental results

The experimental results lead to the following conclusions:

1. The penetrant enhanced X-ray radiography can give detailed information on the nature and distribution of damage in graphite/epoxy laminates. It can find matrix cracks and delaminations.

2. Failure in notched composite laminates takes the form of damage zone expanding in the vicinity of notches and delaminations in some case.

3. The damage zone in the lamina mainly takes the form of matrix cracks and there are few fiber fracture.

Figure 4 Radiographic image of ply damage at $0.937 S_c$ in Specimen CA1-1

Numerical Model and Analysis

In order to predict the damage growth in the notched composite laminates with numerical method, three problems must be solved firstly. 1) What theoretical model is used to determine the stress distribution in the composite laminates? 2) What criterion is used to define the damage growth? 3) How is the constitutive relation of materials after damage occurring set up?

Stress Analysis

Stress is an important mechanical parameter which is used to define whether the materials fail. The tendency of the stress distribution has a directly effect on failure process of materials. The stress analysis on the composite laminates with an edge crack (5) indicated that the classical lamination theory could be used to define the stress distribution in the laminates with notches under the certain condition.

Failure Criterion

In the present study, Tsai-Wu theory is used to define the damage growth in the laminates. Considering the classical lamination theory is used, the strain is constant along the thickness. The criterion in the strain space would be conducive to the calculation:

$$\epsilon^T C_1^i + \epsilon^T C_2^i \epsilon = 1 \quad (1)$$

ϵ and i respectively show the vector of strain in plane under the structure coordinate and the i th ply. In the procedure of finite element analysis, the damage is assumed to occur when the left side of Equation 1 exceeds unity. Equation 1 only indicates when the damage occurs, it does not define the failure mode.

Constitutive Relation After Damage Occurring

The constitutive relations that have been advanced were put forward in accordance with the failure mode of the unnotched composites, nevertheless the failure mechanism in the notched composites is different from that in the unnotched composites(?). According to the observation in the experiments, the damage zone in the lamina mainly takes the form of matrix cracks. The failure mode should be established from knowledge of failure mechanism. On the premise that the materials after damage occurring satisfy the hypothesis of continuity, assume:

$$E_{22}^i = G_{12}^i \nu_{12}^i = 0 \quad (2)$$

According to Ref. 6, the modulus in the fiber direction of composites can be expressed as:

$$E_{11} = E_f V_f + E_m V_m \quad (3)$$

Considering the contribution of matrix in composites at present in the longitudinal modulus is only about one percent to two percent, the modulus in the fiber direction after damage occurring can be defined:

$$\bar{E}_{11}^i = 0.985 E_{11}^i \quad (4)$$

From the elementary equations in the mechanics of composite materials, the new constitutive equation after damage occurring could be established.

The failure process in the uniaxial tension $(0/90)_{4S}$ and $(0/\pm 45/90)_{2S}$ unnotched specimens have been analyzed using the model mentioned above. The comparison of numerical results with experimental results indicates that this hypothesis could well imitate the mechanical response of the materials (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6).

Figure 5 Stress vs strain, $(0/\pm 45/90)_{2S}$ laminates in uniaxial tension

Figure 6 Stress vs strain, $(0/90)_{4S}$ laminates in uniaxial tension

Results and Discussion

In the present study, the mixed solution (that is an iterative incremental loading procedure which reduces the nonlinear problem to a sequence of linear problems) is used to solve the nonlinear simultaneous equations. In order to determine the damage zone accurately and continuously, the eight noded isoparametric element is used. The material properties used in the analysis are given in Table I. The specimen dimensions and geometry for Specimen CA1-1 are specified as follows: $L=250\text{mm}$, $W=38\text{mm}$, $R=3\text{mm}$, $a=1\text{mm}$, $t=2.1\text{mm}$. The material and geometrical symmetry permit that only one quarter of the specimen be examined. There are total 99 elements and 342 nodes.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 illustrate the damage zone growth predicted according to the present model. Before 30% failure load, the damage zone in the 0-deg and 90-deg plies is still confined in the vicinity of the notch tips. The damage zone in the 90-deg plies expands rapidly and almost reaches the whole 90-deg plies at 40% failure load. Compared with the experimental results, the growth of the damage zone predicted is faster than that in real case but it is consistent with the experimental results in the tendency.

The damage zone in the 0-deg plies is smaller than that in the 90-deg plies and mainly expands along the fiber, this is consistent with the actual damage growth. According to the present model, this damage zone in each ply appears like a subcrack in this region. The stress relaxation must arise so that the damage zone is restrained to grow along original cracks and is permitted to grow along the fiber.

Owing to the expanding of the damage zone in the 0-deg plies, there must be stress relaxation behind the crack tips. The low stress region (corresponding to $\sigma_{ij}/\sigma_{\infty}$) will expand larger and larger and stress in this region will scarcely increase. This can be explained by the fact that the damage zone in

this region in the 90-deg plies hardly expands.

Table I Material properties of the lamina in the laminates

Modulus (kg/mm ²)	$E_{11} = 10 \cdot 10^5$ $G_{12} = 0.53 \cdot 10^5$	$E_{22} = 0.9 \cdot 10^5$ $\nu_{12} = 0.31$
Strength (kg/mm ²)	$X = 11500$ $Y = 280$ $S = 456$	$X' = 8000$ $Y' = 1000$

Figure 7 Damage zone in the 90-deg plies predicted with load increasing in accordance with the present model

Figure 8 Damage zone in the 0-deg plies predicted with load increasing in accordance with the present model

Figure 9 Damage zone prediction at $1.0 S_C$ from the present model (straight lines indicate the matrix cracks drawn according to Figure 4)

Figure 10 Damage zone prediction at $1.0 S_C$ from the complete elastic model

Figure 11 Damage zone prediction at $1.0 S_C$ from the complete discount model

Figure 10 and Figure 11 illustrate the ultimate damage zone predicted according to two another hypotheses, that is the complete elastic model and the complete discount model. Undoubtedly, those are two ultimate cases. Through the comparison of results from three hypotheses (Fig. 9, Fig. 10 and Fig. 11), it can be seen that three results are covered each other, the damage zone from one hypothesis does not include another one. This conclusion is not consistent with Ref. 3. In Ref. 3, two hypotheses mentioned above were considered to give the upper and lower bound of the damage zone. The results of the present study indicate that the stress and strain in the materials will be redistributed with the development of the damage and the region existing stress concentration will transform, this will result in the change of the tendency of the damage expanding. Therefore, the damage zones predicted in accordance with three hypotheses are different from each other and the failure processes of the materials represented are also different from each other.

From the above discussion, it can be seen that how the constitutive relation of the materials after damage occurring to be established is very important. Under the macroscopic case, the damage growth in the composite materials is represented by the redistribution of stress and strain. However, stress and strain relation is a main factor which has an effect on the redistribution of stress and strain.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The cumulative damage data developed in this study with experimental and numerical methods indicate that the damage in the materials has already occurred at rather low load and expands rapidly with load increasing.

The comparison of the numerical results and the experimental results indicates that the numerical model could well imitate the real damage growth to certain degree under the condition of reasonable establishment of the constitutive relation of the materials. The present model in accordance with the failure model from the observation in the experiments fairly represents the phenomenon of stress relaxation after damage occurring.

From the experimental results, it can be seen that the damage in the composite laminates also includes delaminations. In order to understand the failure process in the materials completely, it is necessary to set up three dimensional analysis method. Moreover, it is rather insufficient to study the damage under the macroscopic case. In the future work, the heterogeneity of the materials and the interactions between the components of the materials must be considered. Only on this way, the criterion that predict the fracture of the composite materials could be established reasonably.

References

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